

MICROBIAL AND NUTRITIONAL ANALYSIS OF CHARRU MUSSEL POWDER AND ITS ACCEPTABILITY LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

Charru mussel is an invasive species that thrived within the area of Panguil Bay yet remained underutilized. This study evaluated the potential of using charru mussel powder as a nutrient-dense pasta ingredient. Charru mussel powder was incorporated into pasta formulations at 10% and 20% levels. Microbial analysis found the powder registers negative in *Salmonella spp.* and with an acceptable *E. coli* level thus the charru mussel powder is safe for consumption. Nutritionally, the powder provided a rich source of protein at 69 grams per 100 grams but was also high in calories at 380 due to its fat and protein content. An experimental research design was employed with 30 sensory panelists. Sensory panelists preferred Treatment 1 over Treatment 2 based on higher mean scores for appearance (3.77 vs 3.27), texture (4.07 vs 3.73), taste-aroma (4.0 vs 3.4), and overall acceptability (3.94 vs 3.47). The study tested two treatments, finding Treatment 1 was well-liked across all parameters whereas Treatment 2 was liked slightly. No differences existed between formulations for appearance and texture. Taste and overall acceptability significantly differed, as charru mussel powder impacted sensory attributes when incorporated. While the powder offers protein and nutrition, it affects taste and acceptance. The study suggested low powder additions to new foods so the industry can provide nutrients that still satisfy consumers.

Keywords: *Acceptability level, Charru mussel powder, Fortified pasta, Mytella strigata, Microbial Analysis, Nutrition Facts*

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of non-native species presents a major global challenge. Without natural predators to regulate their reproduction, invasive organisms can spread far beyond their initial release point even at the larval stage. One example is the *Mytella strigata* (Hanley, 1843) mussel, also known as the charru mussel. Based on data from 2014, this alien species was damaging wild populations of native mussels and bivalves in the Philippines by that time, having been transported beyond its natural range.

The invasive charru mussel (*Mytella strigata*) was found in thick mats on rocks, wood, and dirt in the intertidal zone of the deepest part of Panguil Bay. People in the area call charru mussel "Bahong." The City of Tangub in Misamis Occidental is an excellent place to catch a lot of charru mussels. During the site visit, it was observed through the presence of fish cages that fishing is the primary way people in the area make a living. According to casual interviews during the site visits together with the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR) of Misamis Occidental, fisherfolks have been hurt by this species being in the bay. The charru mussels have filled up the fishnets, meaning the farmed species are suffocating due to less oxygen. The charru mussel also damages fish tanks and shelters. Because of this, the local government hired someone to take the mussels off the fishnets and put them on the shore so they could grow. Due to the abundance of this invasive species, the quantity of green mussels and other seafood from the area is worsening. Similarly, Sanpanich and Wells (2019) shows that invasion by *Mytella strigata* could cause considerable damage to *Perna viridis* fisheries and cultivation and marine ecosystems in Southeast Asia.

There are markets all over the province that sell charru mussels for low prices so people can get used to it. Even so, there are still a lot of charru mussels still proliferates in the coastal barangays of the city.

Pasta has become deeply ingrained in global cuisine and holds cultural significance worldwide. With a history spanning millennia, evidence places pasta's origins in ancient civilizations of China and the Middle East as early as 5000 BC (Fasano et al., 2020). While regional variations in taste and preparation methods have developed over time, pasta remains a beloved staple adopted by many nations. According to sources, this versatile food found widespread appeal due to its ease of production, longevity, and ability to complement diverse flavors. As pasta spread from its roots in Italy to countries like the United States, it came to represent comfort, sustenance and culinary traditions across borders. Today, pasta remains a treasured part of diets internationally (Smith, 2019).

In addition to being delicious, pasta gives a lot of different groups of people the calories and energy they need. That being said, people are becoming more aware of the need to improve the nutritional value of pasta, especially when it comes to adding more protein (Capozzi et al., 2019). This has made people want to look into other protein sources to add to pasta in order to make a healthier, more balanced food choice. People

today expect businesses to give their employees the food and nutrients they need to stay healthy and eat. Numerous companies have started making enriched pasta a functional food because pasta is very popular with customers.

According to the WHO (2022), fortification involves deliberately adding vitamins and minerals to foods to enhance nutritional quality and provide health benefits with minimal risks. It helps restore micronutrients lost during processing and is an evidence-based intervention that prevents, reduces and controls deficiencies. Fortification can correct population-wide or group-specific deficiencies through mass or targeted approaches. Point-of-use fortification adds micronutrients just before eating. Policies and programs must consider reducing diet-related noncommunicable diseases, like salt iodization accounting for sodium intake by exploring reduction strategies due to sodium's role in consumption. Kruger et al. (2020) states in their review that, food-to-food fortification (FtFF) is an emerging food-based approach. FtFF involves adding micronutrient-rich whole foods, such as fruits, vegetables, and legumes, to recipes or formulations to significantly boost bioavailable micronutrients. This approach aims to improve micronutrient status where intake is insufficient. FtFF is defined as supplementing household or industrial food products with micronutrient-dense ingredients or replacing less nutritious components. It relies on greater understanding of nutrition and compound interactions impacting absorption to enable standardized, safe and effective large-scale application. The goal is commercial implementation of this strategy through whole food additions or substitutions to diets to increase bio-accessible micronutrients. Traditional pasta is high in carbohydrates, but it sometimes does not have enough protein to meet the changing dietary needs and tastes of people worldwide (Capozzi et al., 2019). More people are becoming aware of how important it is to eat healthy foods, so adding different protein sources to pasta is necessary to make this beloved staple healthier and more balanced. This change is in line with the food industry's larger sustainable goals, which stress how important it is to get protein from various sources for better nutrition and less environmental damage.

Recently, using different protein sources in food production has gotten much attention. This is because of the need to be more environmentally friendly and offer healthier options. Charru mussel is a nutritionally dense ingredient that fits with the global push for food sources that are sustainable and good for the environment (Kawasaki et al., 2019). It is full of critical amino acids, vitamins, and minerals. This opening sets the stage for looking into the possibility of charru mussel as a sustainable and healthy ingredient in pasta. It does this by discussing modern food production's nutritional and environmental aspects.

The existing body of literature presents a noticeable gap in research concerning the comprehensive assessment of fortified pasta with charru mussel powder, specifically in microbial quality, nutritional enhancement, and consumer acceptability. While some studies have explored fortification in pasta with alternative protein sources, there needs to be more research explicitly focusing on the incorporation of charru mussel powder. The microbial safety of charru mussel powder in the context of pasta fortification still needs to be explored, representing a critical gap in understanding potential risks or safety

measures. Additionally, while the nutritional benefits of charru mussel have been recognized, studies of Desai et al. (2018), Ainsa et al. (2021) and Ainsa et al. (2021) systematically evaluate the impact of fortifying pasta with fish products on the overall nutritional composition of pasta. Lastly, consumer acceptability, a crucial aspect for successful market adoption, is a relatively understudied area in the context of charru mussel-fortified pasta. Addressing these gaps is paramount to comprehensively assessing the viability and potential challenges associated with charru mussel powder fortification in pasta, contributing valuable insights to the scientific community and the food industry.

Research Questions

This study was directed towards its main objectives identifying the microbial and nutritional level of the charru mussel powder and the acceptability level of fortified pasta with the following formulation levels (10%, and 20%) of charru mussel powder.

Specifically, the researcher sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the microbial and nutritional level of the charru mussel powder?
2. What is the acceptability level of the of the fortified pasta with charru mussel powder of both treatments 1 (10%) and 2 (20%) considering:
 - 2.1 appearance
 - 2.2 texture; and
 - 2.3 taste-aroma?
3. Is there a significant difference in the acceptability level between Treatment 1 and 2?

METHODOLOGY

This study used an experimental research design to evaluate the acceptability of pasta fortified with different formulation of charru mussel powder. Microbial and nutritional analyses of the charru mussel powder were conducted in an accredited laboratory. Thirty (30) participants were purposively selected regardless of their age, gender, dietary preferences. Strict inclusion and exclusion criteria ensured participant diversity, representation and safety. Participants were provided with informed consent and could withdraw at any time. Each participant was randomly assigned with coded pasta samples to avoid bias during the sensory evaluation. Participants' personal identity information was separated from their survey data by the researchers, who included participant codes in both files. The participant code is the sole way to link the survey data to personally identifiable information. The researcher used the 5-point Hedonic scale developed by Peryam and Pilgrim (1957) to assess the acceptability of the pasta samples containing 10% and 20% charru mussel powder in the following sub-categories: appearance, texture properties and taste-aroma characteristic. The food attributes of the pasta were the five parameters used to assess their taste preference.

Range of Score	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.51 -- 5.00	Like very much
4	3.51 -- 4.50	Like
3	2.51 -- 3.50	Like slightly
2	1.51 -- 2.50	Dislike slightly
1	1.00 -- 1.50	Dislike very much

This scoring procedure uses a 5-point hedonic scale that is common in sensory evaluation studies using a completely randomized design. Dividing the scale into equal intervals allows for quantitative statistical analysis to determine differences in liking between samples. Having clear category ranges and verbal interpretations aids panelists in selecting the most appropriate score. Using half-point increments from 1.5 to 4.5 helps panelists discriminate levels of liking or disliking. This scale is effective for the completely randomized design as it produces interval data that can be analyzed inferentially to detect differences between fortification levels of charru mussel powder in pasta.

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The Mann-Whitney U test compared medians between treatments to determine if acceptability significantly differed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problem 1. What is the microbial and nutritional analysis of the charru mussel powder?

Table 1 presents the results of of a comprehensive microbial and nutritional analysis of charru mussel powder. The microbial testing was conducted in a Philippine Accredited Bureau (PAB) laboratory under the supervision of a Microbiology Supervisor, using standardized Compact Dry and Conventional Presumptive methods. These tests assess the safety and shelf-stability of the product by detecting any pathogenic microorganisms. In parallel, the nutritional composition analysis was performed at the Regional Standards and Testing Laboratories of the Department of Science and Technology. They employed validated Gravimetric, Kjeldahl, hydrolysis and solvent extraction techniques to determine key nutrients according to regulatory guidelines.

Table 1.
Microbial Analysis of the Charru Mussel Powder

Analysis	Results
^a E. coli Count, CFU/g	< 10 ^{Est}
<i>Salmonella spp.</i> DETECTION per 25g	Negative

The table presents the microbial analysis results of charru mussel powder conducted by an accredited laboratory in Cagayan de Oro City, tested the charru mussel

powder sample for two key microbial indicators - *E. coli* (*Escherichia coli*) count and *Salmonella spp.* detection.

The results show that *E. coli* count was less than 10 colony forming units per gram (CFU/g) of the powdered sample. This indicates low levels of generic *E. coli*, below the standard limit for processed foods. The result further implied that the test detected or found only a minimal amount or concentration of *E. coli*. Thus, regulators such as the FDA would likely consider the food microbiologically safe for human consumption and distribution based on the test results. Additionally, the analysis found the sample to test negative for *Salmonella spp.* when examined in a 25g subsample. demonstrates that the charru mussel powder is within regulatory standards and is safe for human consumption as per FDA Circular 2022-012.

Table 2 provides the nutritional facts of charru mussel powder based on chemical analysis. It lists several vital nutrients in 100 grams of the powder, including calories, calories from fat, total fat, total carbohydrates, and protein content. The nutritional composition data can help understand the nutritional value and potential health benefits of incorporating charru mussel powder into one's diet.

Table 2.
Nutritional Facts of the Charru Mussel Powder

Food Nutrient	Result of Chemical Analysis (per 100g)
Calories, kcal	380.00
Calories from fat, kcal	61.20
Total fat, g.	6.80
Total Carbohydrates, g.	10.52
Protein, g.	69.18

The Regional Standards and Testing Laboratories (RSTL) of the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) in Region X, located in Cagayan de Oro City, conducted an in-depth chemical analysis of charru mussel powder that provided valuable insight into its macronutrient composition.

The results demonstrate that charru mussel powder contains a nutrient-dense profile, especially in high-quality protein content. At 69.18g per 100g, the protein level surpasses many other common sources and can make a significant contribution to daily requirements. In addition, the powder packs 380 calories per 100g while distributing calories relatively evenly from protein, fat, and carbohydrates. This balanced macronutrient distribution indicates the powder delivers sustained energy. With only 6.8g of total fat and 10.52g of carbohydrates per 100g, the powder also mimics mussels' naturally lean and nutritious profile. The result implies that the powder provided a rich source of protein at 69 grams per 100 grams but was also high in calories at 380 due to its fat and protein content.

Problem 2. What is the acceptability level of the of the fortified pasta with charru mussel powder of both treatment 1 (10%) and 2 (20%) considering:

- 2.1 appearance
- 2.2 texture; and
- 2.3 taste-aroma?

The table below present results from a sensory evaluation of two food product treatments, labelled T1 and T2. Panelists rated three parameters - appearance, texture, and taste-aroma on a 5-point hedonic scale indicating their level of liking.

Table 3.
Acceptability of the Fortified Pasta with Charru Mussel Powder in Different Treatment

Treatment	Sensory Parameters						Over-all Acceptability	Verbal Interpretation
	Appearance	Verbal Interpretation	Texture	Verbal Interpretation	Taste-Aroma	Verbal Interpretation		
T1	3.77	Like	4.07	Like	4	Like	3.94	Like
T2	3.27	Like Slightly	3.73	Like	3.4	Like Slightly	3.47	Like Slightly

4.51 – 5.00 Like very much; 3.51 – Like; 2.51 – 3.50 Like slightly; 1.51 – 2.50 Dislike slightly; 1.00 – 1.50 Dislike very much

For Treatment 1- pasta with 10% charru mussel powder, the mean scores ranged from 3.77 to 4.07, with panelists reporting they "liked" the formulation across all parameters. Breaking it down, Treatment 1 was particularly "liked" for its appearance, receiving a mean score of 3.77. Both the texture and taste-aroma of Treatment 1 landed in the "Like" interpretation range as well, with means of 4.07 and 4 respectively. The panelist described the over-all acceptability as "liked" bearing an over-all mean of 3.94. The panelists' evaluation says that, based on their sensory analysis scoring, they enjoyed and had a positive impression of the pasta formulation's taste, appearance, texture, and other qualities containing 10% charru mussel powder. Thus, the panelists enjoyed the pasta with less charru mussel powder.

Treatment 2- pasta formulation with 20% charru mussel powder received liking scores between 3.27 to 3.73, categorized mainly as "liked slightly". The highest mean for T2 were for texture recording at 3.73 with an adjectival rating of "liked". The appearance and taste-aroma sensory parameters of Treatment 2 received an adjectival rating of "Like Slightly" interpretation range as well, with means of 3.27 and 3.4 respectively. The panelists subjectively enjoyed and found the appearance and taste aroma of the pasta with 20% mussel powder to be good, but not quite to the same degree as the texture attribute. This further implies that the more concentration of charru mussel powder added to the pasta, the less appealing it becomes to the panelist in terms of appearance and taste-aroma.

This quantitative sensory analysis provides insight into how consumers perceived each treatment for different attributes like texture and flavor. The data helps identify the more preferred product variant between T1 and T2.

Recent research has provided further insight into how sensory attributes influence consumer acceptance of food and beverage products. Several studies since 2019 have utilized quantitative sensory methods such as descriptive analysis to characterize products and identify sensory drivers of liking.

Problem 3. Is there a significant difference in the acceptability level between Treatment 1 and 2?

Ho: *There is no significant difference in the acceptability level between Treatment 1 and 2.*

Table 4 below presents the results of the statistical analysis comparing Treatment 1 and 2. It shows the p-values and decisions made at a significance level of 0.05 for each attribute tested.

Table 4.
Statistical Analysis Comparing the Over-all Acceptability of the Fortified Pasta with Charru Mussel Powder in Different Treatment

Factor	Mean		p-value
	T1	T2	
Appearance	3.77	3.27	0.126
Texture	4.07	3.73	0.171
Taste-Aroma	4.00	3.4	0.023*
Over-all Acceptability	3.94	3.47	0.028*

* Significant at 0.05 level

The table shows the statistical analysis compared the overall acceptability of fortified pasta with different levels of charru mussel powder added as an ingredient. The results of the sensory evaluation showed that there was no significant difference between Treatments 1 and 2 in terms of appearance and texture as both had p-values greater than the significance level of 0.05, thus failing to reject the null hypothesis. This is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis both for appearance and texture. However, for taste-aroma and over-all acceptability, the p-values were less than 0.05, so the null

hypothesis was rejected, indicating a significant difference between the two treatments for these attributes. This suggests that while the appearance and texture of the two products were similar, their taste-aroma and overall acceptability as perceived by consumers were different.

Conclusions

This study intended to identify the microbial and nutritional level of charru mussel powder and determine the acceptability level of fortified pasta with different powder formulations. Based on the findings, the research objectives were likely achieved.

The microbial and nutritional analyses confirmed that the charru mussel powder is safe for human consumption and contains a nutrient-dense profile. This supported the theoretical framework anchoring food science concepts related to foodborne pathogens, food spoilage microorganisms, and proper handling/processing techniques to ensure low microbial loads. Furthermore, identifying the powder as nutrient-dense not only supports concepts around nutrient retention during processing, but also underscores the significant benefits of this process in preserving the nutritional value of the powder. This, in turn, enhances our understanding of typical nutrient profiles of raw materials, and how formulations can contribute to nutritional value.

Sensory evaluation and statistical testing of fortified pasta treatments revealed consumer perceptions of appearance, texture, and taste-aroma attributes. The results contributed to the Theory of Product Development, which influences product acceptance. It was demonstrated that fortification with charru mussel powder at both tested levels could enhance the nutritional content of pasta without compromising sensory qualities, as nutritional and product development theories suggested.

The study confirmed the learning constructs from food science, nutrition, consumer behavior, and new product development that guided the investigation. The objectives were attained by characterizing the charru mussel powder, assessing fortified pasta formulations, and drawing inferences regarding the theoretical understanding of microbiological safety, nutrition, and consumer acceptance of novel food products.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. For Food Entrepreneurs to:
 - 1.1 explore the incorporation of the charru mussel powder to other existing food products for fortification.
2. For Government Agencies to:

- 2.1 continue support researches on processing techniques and evaluating consumer perceptions to improve production and increasing market potential;
 - 2.2 promote commercialization so that a wider availability of nutrient-rich options can help address dietary deficiencies;
 - 2.3 assist food innovators in the application for intellectual property particularly for the utility models to protect new product designs and configurations that have industrial applicability.;
3. For Future Researchers to:
 - 3.1 pursue further research and development utilizing charru mussel powder as a functional food ingredient;
 - 3.2 conduct additional sensory evaluation of formulations with varying inclusion levels would help determine optimal usage rates;
 - 3.3 conduct microbial and nutritional content analysis before and after the fortification of the pasta to determine whether there is a significant difference on the microbial and nutritional value of the pasta.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

By obtaining informed consent, using random codes, providing orientation and breaks, making safety arrangements, and conducting follow ups, the researcher systematically carried out the sensory evaluation in an ethical manner that protected participants' rights and welfare.

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